

Article

A Methodology for Network Analysis to Improve the Cyber-Physicals Communications in Next-Generation Networks

David Cortés-Polo ^{*}

Research, Technological Innovation and Supercomputing Center of Extremadura (CénitS), National Road 521, km 41.8, 10071 Cáceres, Spain; luisignacio.jimenez@cenits.es (L.I.J.G.); joseluis.gonzalez@cenits.es (J.-L.G.-S.); jesus.calle@cenits.es (J.C.-C.)

* Correspondence: david.cortes@cenits.es

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Abstract: Cyber-physical systems allow creating new applications and services which will bring people, data, processes, and things together. The network is the backbone that interconnects this new paradigm, especially 5G networks that will expand the coverage, reduce the latency, and enhance the data rate. In this sense, network analytics will increase the knowledge about the network and its interconnected devices, being a key feature especially with the increment in the number of physical things (sensors, actuators, smartphones, tablets, and so on). With this increment, the usage of online networking services and applications will grow, and network operators require to detect and analyze all issues related to the network. In this article, a methodology to analyze real network information provided by a network operator and acquire knowledge of the communications is presented. Various real data sets, provided by Telecom Italia, are analyzed to compare two different zones: one located in the urban area of Milan, Italy, and its surroundings, and the second in the province of Trento, Italy. These data sets describe different areas and shapes that cover a metropolitan area in the first case and a mainly rural area in the second case, which implies that these areas will have different compartments. To compare these compartments and group them in a single cluster set, a new technique is presented in this paper to establish a relationship between them and reduce those that could be similar.

Keywords: 5G; data analysis; mobile networks; network analytic; cyber-physical systems

1. Introduction

The number of heterogeneous systems connected to the Internet is growing exponentially. In 2022, it is expected that 28.5 billion devices will be connected [1], driven by the appearance of networked devices such as embedded devices, smartphones, smart tables, sensors, radio-frequency identification, and actuators, which use new services and applications. With this emergence, the cyber-physical systems (CPS) acquire a new dimension. CPS represent a new generation of digital systems, which consists of the advanced connectivity, which ensures real-time data acquisition from the physical world and the information feedback from the cyberspace, and the intelligent data management, which adds the analytical and computational capability that constructs the cyberspace [2]. The increment of a huge number of CPS devices onto cellular networks will quickly overload the network, causing performance degradation to cellular users on one hand, and on the other hand, preventing CPS to take advantage of global connectivity, ubiquitous coverage, reliability, and security features of cellular networks [3].

To provide the advanced connectivity to CPS, 5G technology is considered as one of the most important, because it integrates entities, communications, and control technologies [4,5], as 5G

of the data set, analyzing the usage profile of the network classified in a particular scenario, i.e., a big city like Milan, can be found in other scenarios, like those described in Trento province. This is because there are characteristics that can be inferred from the compartment of the network due to the spatio-temporal relationship with the mobile network usage. This relationship is useful to network managers in controlling the connectivity of a huge number of devices, as is required in cyber-physical systems.

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